

POLICE ETHICAL CONDUCT AND CRIME REPORTING IN SOUTHERN SENATORIAL DISTRICT OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between police ethical practices and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study assessed the relationship between police brutality, unlawful detention and crime reporting. The study adopted cross-sectional survey research design. Data were gathered from both primary and secondary sources. This study made use of Strain Theory, which offers insight into ethical dilemmas within law enforcement. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select sample size of one thousand two hundred respondents. A self-report questionnaire and IDI guide developed by researcher and approved by the supervisors was used as instrument for data collection. The obtained data were statistically analysed using simple linear regression while the in-depth interview data was analysed using content analysis. The result obtained from the analysis revealed that, police brutality, extortion and police interrogation significantly relate to crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study recommended among other things that police authority should organize regular training for police officers on human rights, conflict resolution, and de-escalation techniques in order to reduce incidents of brutality. The government with civil organizations should establish independent oversight bodies to investigate complaints of police brutality which would help restore public confidence and encourage reporting.

Keywords: police ethical conduct, police brutality, unlawful detention, and crime reporting

INTRODUCTION

Ethics is the basis of all kinds of human relationships, thus wherever there is an individual, there exists an absolute ethical relationship that should not be overlooked (Oyeleke, 2021). Ethical behaviour is characterized by honesty, fairness and equity in interpersonal, professional, and academic relationship and it respects the dignity, diversity, and the right of individual and groups of people (Ogunnaiké, 2021). Ethical conduct in police institution has been a matter of public policy concern since the inception of police organizations. As the need for police arose, definitions of proper conduct became increasingly important. In addition to existing regulatory rules, professional ethical principles are needed for police officers to raise the standards and quality of services they provide, considering the breadth of powers held by security personnel in law enforcement. The healthy operation of security services and the mitigation of human

rights abuses depend on the establishment and acceptance of professional ethical principles and rules by police officers (Arisukwu, 2012).

Historically, and despite structural changes to curb it, police misconduct has existed as long as there have been police, and it remained a continuing problem throughout the history of policing (Brunson & Wade, 2020). Before the advent of organised policing characterised by the inception of the Metropolitan Police in England in 1829 (Chidiebere-Mark, 2018), officials responsible for providing law enforcement services were involved in corrupt acts. However, with the introduction of the first formalised police bureaucracy, measures were taken amongst other objectives to minimise corruption among police officers. To curb corruption, the police became highly centralised, and emphasis was placed on procedural regularity, impersonal authority, and limited discretion (Jang & Agnew, 2015). Despite all these measures, police misconduct is still a serious problem in the United States of America (USA), England and other developed countries. Allegations of police misconduct, discrimination, nepotism, bribery, intimidation-provoking, neglect, exploitation, selfishness, corruption, torture, cozying-flattery, violence, oppression, aggression, mixing policy in relationships, insults and curses, physical and sexual abuse, bad habits, abuse of power and duty, gossip, embezzlement, dogmatic behaviour, and subservience, sycophancy, brutality, and harassment have popped up all over the USA and other developed societies of the world (Hadley, 2021).

The police institutions in most Africa countries have recently been in the limelight for various conducts like corruption, abuse of power, police brutality, lack of accountability, etc., not befitting the profession. The institution has witnessed an increase in disciplinary and criminal charges by police officers leading to their reprimand, dismissal, and imprisonment (Gwaza & Kumar, 2023). According to Gwaza and Kumar (2023) the Malawi Police Service (MPS) Professional Standards Unit, the Office of Ombudsman and Police Service Commission have been awash with complaints against the Police. Members of public have lodged complaints such as excessive use of force, misuse of public office, abuse of authority and corruption among others (Alao & Adeyemi, 2019). A 2021 Transparency International Report rated Malawi Police Service (MPS) as the most corrupt department in Malawi's public sector. Similarity, in South Africa, the police have been accused of excessive use of force resulting in wrongful death while in the line of duty, or forging reports to support or reinforce false claims. Other unethical behaviours considered unbecoming of police officers in South Africa include theft of confiscated evidence, selling drugs, nepotism, fraternization, and immorality (Wankhar & Diana, 2018). Every unethical behaviour exhibited by police officers not only damage the image of the police force but also reduce public confidence in police institution (Singgih et' al, 2018). According to Budiarto and Nurmalisa (2018), when police officers fail to do what is right, they erode public trust and further degrade the law enforcing ability. Police unethical conduct is the primary contributor to negative perceptions and decreased community satisfaction (Payam, 2016).

For many years, the relationship between the Nigerian police force and the citizen has been poor due to a lengthy history of unethical conduct and unprofessional acts of the NPF (Afolabi et' al, 2021). The Nigeria police force have wandered away from their primary assignments of protecting lives and property to harassing, killing, and extorting those they have sworn an oath to protect. As noted by Oluwafifehan (2019), there is growing concern among the Nigerian populace regarding unprofessional activities and behaviour of Nigerian police officers which

includes pay offs on the roads, bribery, extortion, and false accusations on ordinary citizens. These have further damaged public trust in the Nigerian Police force such that the citizens see police officers as enemies. In the same vein, Omilana (2019) argued that the character of Nigerian Police Force has been associated with brutality, extra-judicial killings, unlawful detention of suspects, demanding payment for bail, search, and arrest without warrants, mounting of illegal roadblocks for the purpose of extorting money, use of alcohol and other drugs, harassment, and intimidation of political opponents of ruling parties.

Human rights watch groups (2018) also attest that Nigerian citizens have been killed indiscriminately by the police. For example, Egun Timilehin, a nine- year-old girl was killed by a stray bullet triggered by a SARS operative in Lagos in an unsuccessful attempt to extort money from a commercial bus driver at the checkpoint. In March 2019, SARS operatives, to arrest one of the boys of a major music producer, killed a man named Kolade Johnson. Kolade was said to be watching a football match in a cinema remarkably close to his area at Mangoro, Ikeja, Lagos (Victor, et al., 2019). These ethical practices by the police have increased tension between the populace and Nigerians as seen by the increase in cases of mob justice and burning down of institutional structure (police officers and infrastructure) due to what analysts believe to be loss of trust in police service and formal justice delivery system (Victor, Chika & Innocent, 2019). According to Skogan (2016) the unprofessional conduct of individual police officers, have made citizens feel uncomfortable or unsafe reporting crimes to them, because they consider them irrelevant or ill-prepared to handle the problem of crime, force. Humana Right Watch, (2010) cited a long history of engaging in unprofessional, corrupt, and criminal conduct, and using excessive and often brutal force as the reason why crime reporting is reasonably low in Nigeria.

Arifiyani and Sukimo (2012) assert that some police officers act unethically because their ethical standard does not align with that of the police institution, and they may be driven by a desire to secure personal gain. The many needs that remain unfulfilled force police officers to engage in unethical behaviour for the purpose of securing more personal gains. Efforts such as training, legislative reforms and whistle-blower policy aimed at addressing the problem of police ethical practices have been ongoing. Various stakeholders, including government bodies, law enforcement agencies, advocacy groups, and communities, have implemented a range of strategies to promote accountability, transparency, and ethical conduct within police forces.

Although available literature suggested that fear of stigmatisation, fear of reprisals, trauma, distance from police station, severity of the crime among other factors (Human Right Watch, 2010; Victor, et al., 2019) are some of the main reasons for non-reporting of crime very little is known about the relationship between police ethical practices and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between police ethical practices and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. Understanding why victims report or fail to report crimes is crucial for the development and implementation of crime control strategies because it helps to identify the barriers that prevent victims from reporting crimes.

Objective of the study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between police ethical practices and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

Examine the relationship between police brutality and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Determine the relationship between unlawful detention and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria

Statement of hypotheses

Police brutality has no significant relationship with crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria

Unlawful detention does not significantly relate to crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria

Theoretical underpinning

Strain Theory

Strain Theory, first developed by Robert K. Merton in 1938, builds on Émile Durkheim's concept of anomie to explain how social structures influence deviant behaviour. According to Merton, every society establishes culturally approved goals, such as wealth, success, or upward mobility, and also prescribes the legitimate means such as education, employment, or hard work by which individuals are expected to attain these goals. However, when there is a disjunction between the goals and the accessible means, individuals experience what he termed strain. This strain creates pressure that may lead people to adapt in different ways. While some conform to both the goals and means, others may innovate by pursuing the goals through illegitimate avenues. Still others may ritualize, retreat, or rebel against both the goals and the means. In this sense, crime is often viewed as an adaptation to the structural imbalance between societal expectations and the reality of unequal opportunities.

When applied to policing, Strain Theory offers insight into ethical dilemmas within law enforcement. Police officers operate within a structure that sets professional goals, such as the maintenance of law and order and the protection of justice. Yet, they often work under difficult conditions marked by limited resources, low remuneration, and political interference. These constraints can create a form of strain that may push some officers toward unethical practices such as bribery, extortion, or the misuse of power. Such practices become "innovative" but illegitimate ways of meeting the demands of their role. Similarly, Strain Theory sheds light on patterns of crime reporting among citizens. In societies where individuals perceive those legal institutions are unable or unwilling to deliver justice, the disjunction between the cultural goal of security and the ineffective means of achieving it discourages people from reporting crimes. Instead, they may turn to informal justice mechanisms or remain silent, perpetuating cycles of underreporting and mistrust.

Despite its usefulness, Strain Theory has been subject to several criticisms. One of the main critiques is its heavy emphasis on economic success, which does not adequately explain crimes that are not motivated by financial gain, such as crimes of passion or certain forms of white-collar crime. It is also criticized for being overly deterministic, implying that strain almost inevitably leads to deviance, while downplaying individual agency and choice. Furthermore, the theory does not fully account for the role of deviant subcultures, which provide alternative values and norms that sustain criminal behaviour, an area later expanded upon by scholars like Albert Cohen and Cloward and Ohlin. Another limitation is its weak applicability

to white-collar and corporate crimes, which are often committed by individuals who already have access to both cultural goals and legitimate means. Finally, the theory simplifies motivations for crime by focusing narrowly on structural strain, overlooking psychological, situational, and interpersonal factors that also influence deviant behaviour.

Methods

The study adopted the cross-sectional survey research design. Survey research design can be a useful method for studying police ethical practices and crime reporting because it allows the researcher to collect data from a large number of respondents in a standardized and systematic way. The researcher considered this design fit for this study because it allows for both analytical and descriptive representation of results.

This study area was Cross River State, Nigeria. Cross River State stretches between longitude 8.3410° E and Latitude 4.9587° N. The state shares borders with Benue State to the north, Enugu State to the west, Ebonyi and Abia states to the northwest, Akwa Ibom to the east, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south. There are 18 local government areas (LGAs) in the state divided into three senatorial districts: Southern comprising of Akamkpa, Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Calabar Municipal, Biase, Calabar South and Odukpani, Central senatorial district comprises of Abi, Boki, Etung, Ikom, Obubra and Yakuur while the Northern senatorial district comprise of Obanliku, Obudu, Ogoja, Bekwarra, and Yala. Cross River State is characterized by diverse geographical features, including tropical rainforests, mangrove swamps, and rolling hills. The state is traversed by the Cross River, which is one of Nigeria's major rivers and lends its name to the state.

The study population comprised all inhabitants in Cross River State, Nigeria. According to the National Population Census Projection online (2022) the population of Cross River State is 4, 406,200 (four million, four hundred and six thousand, two hundred) people. The sample size comprised respondents who were currently residing in Cross River State, Nigeria. The sample size for this study is three hundred and eighty-four (384) respondents. Survey monkey sample determinant was used to determine the sample size from the total population of the study.

The study adopted multi-stage sampling technique. This technique consists of simple random, purposive, and systematic stratified sampling technique. In stage one, the simple random sampling technique was used to select four (4) Local Government Areas from eighteen (18) Local Government Areas that made up Cross River State, Nigeria. These LGA were selected using the balloting methods of the simple random sampling technique. This was achieved by writing down names of the eighteen Local Government Areas in a piece of paper and put in a small basket where four LGA were randomly selected. The following LGA were selected Akpabuyo, Calabar South, Calabar Municipality, and Odukpani. This four (4) LGA were constitute four (4) clusters of this study. In stage two, the researcher purposively selected two (2) communities from each Local Government Area selected for this study. A total of eight (8) communities were selected, they were: Uwansea and Antigha from Calabar South, Ikot Efa and Ikot Ishie from Calabar Municipality, Ikang, and Idundu from Akpabuyo, and Creek Town and Ankiong from Odukpani Local Government Area.

Finally, to select the actual respondents, systematic random sampling technique was adopted. All living houses in each sampled community were enumerated into even and odd

numbers. Only even numbered houses were systematically sampled in each enumerated cluster and only adults found in those selected houses were given a questionnaire to complete. The technique was used throughout the eight (8) selected communities. From each of the selected communities, forty (48) respondents were selected. The total sample size is 384 respondents.

Data on the study were gathered using a well-structured questionnaire and an in-depth interview guide. The questionnaire contains "closed-ended questions divided into three sections, with each section focusing on a specific segment of the study". The four-point Likert scale questionnaire entitled Police Ethical Practices and crime reporting consists of 16-items. Section A of the questionnaire focused on collecting information on the respondent's demography such as gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation etc. Section B and C consist of items on four- point Likert scale designed to measure the substantive issues of the study. Each item requires the respondents to indicate the frequency of their response under strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (DA), and Strongly Disagreed (SD). The In-depth interview schedule, in like manner, covers similar questions as contained in the research objectives and hypotheses.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical committee of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the stated hypotheses. Each hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Out of a total of 384 copies of questionnaires distributed, only 375 questionnaires were correctly filled and returned giving a response rate of 97.7%. Table 1 shows the classification of respondents based on their demographic characteristics. The gender classification shows that 218 (58.1%) were males while 157 (41.9%) were females. The classification of age ranged as follows, 62(16.5%) respondents were within the range of 20-27 years, 82(21.9%) were within 28-35 years, 147(39.2%) were within the age bracket of 36-43 years, 37(9.9%) were 44-51 years while 47 (12.5%) of the respondents were 52-59 years. Distribution of respondents based on marital status revealed that 95 (25.3%) were single, 260 (69.3%) were married, 10 (2.7%) were divorced/separated while 10 (2.7%) were widowed. The educational classification of respondents shows that 21 (5.6%) had non-formal education, 32 (8.5%) had First School Leaving Certificate, 215 (57.3%) had Senior Secondary School Certificate while 107 (28.5%) are tertiary. The classification of respondents based on religion shows that 206 (54.9%) are Christian, 23 (0.03%) are Islam, 146 (38.9%) are ATR worshippers.

TABLE 1
Demographic characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Sex		
Male	218	58.1
Female	157	41.9
Total	375	100
Age in years		
18-27 years	62	16.5

28-37 years	82	21.9
38-47 years	147	39.2
48-57 years	37	9.9
58 years and above	47	12.5
Total	375	100
Marital status		
Single	95	25.3
Married	260	69.3
Divorced/Separated	10	2.7
Widowed	10	2.7
Total	375	100
Educational status		
Non-formal education	21	5.6
FSLC	32	8.5
SSCE	215	57.3
Tertiary edu	107	28.5
Total	375	100
Christianity	206	54.9
Islam	23	0.03
ATR	146	38.9
Total	375	100

Fieldwork, 2024

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one

Police brutality has no significant relationship with crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this hypothesis is police brutality, while the dependent variable is crime reporting. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypothesis and the result is presented in Table 2

TABLE 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between police brutality and crime reporting

Variable	N	X	SD	r	p-value
Police brutality	375	17.76	3.92	0.621	.000
Crime reporting	375	14.01	3.31		

*Significant at 0.05, df = 373, r-critical=0.139, R2 = 0.386.

Source; Field survey, 2024

The result of the statistical analysis as presented in table 2 indicates that the calculated r-value of 0.621 is greater than the critical p-value at 0.05 level of significance with 373 degree of freedom. This therefore, indicates that there is a significant relationship between police brutality and crime control in Cross River State, Nigeria. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is upheld. The result also shows R2 of 0.386 which indicates that police brutality accounted for 38.6 % of the determinants of crime reporting in the study area.

Hypothesis two

Unlawful detention significantly relate to crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this study is unlawful detention while the dependent variable is crime reporting. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypothesis and the result is presented in Table 3. The result as presented in Table 3 (r=0.534,p=.000) indicated that unlawful detention significantly relate to crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and the alternative hypothesis was retained. The result also shows R2 of 0.285 which indicates that the unlawful detention accounted for 28.5 % of the determinants of crime reporting in the study area.

TABLE 3

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between unlawful detention and crime reporting

Variable	N	X	SD	r-cal	p-level
Unlawful detention	375	16.13	4.13	0.534	.000
Crime reporting	375	14.01	3.31		

*Significant at 0.05, r-critical= 0.139, R2 =0.285, df 373.

Source; Field survey, 2024

Discussion of findings

Police brutality and crime reporting

The findings of statistical analysis for hypothesis one revealed that police brutality has a significant relationship with crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings of this study shows that police brutality can erode trust in law enforcement that can lead individuals to believe that the police will not provide fair or effective responses to crime reports. If people are

hesitant to report crimes due to fear of police brutality, it leads to underreporting. This results in inaccurate crime data, which can hinder effective crime prevention and resource allocation. As a result, they may avoid engaging with the police altogether. The significant relationship between police brutality and crime reporting is supported by a growing body of literature, showing that incidents of police violence often reduce community trust and willingness to report crime. Studies in both the U.S. and globally indicate that communities subjected to frequent police misconduct, particularly in marginalized groups, experience heightened fear and distrust of law enforcement, leading to a reluctance to engage with police services.

Unlawful detention and crime reporting

Findings of this study indicate that unlawful detention significantly relate to crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria. The finding of this study aligns with literature that highlights how such police practices discourage public engagement with law enforcement. Studies on the impact of police misconduct on crime reporting indicate that when law enforcement engages in unlawful detention, it damages trust, deters reporting, and often leads to systemic issues that harm overall community safety and justice. The findings support that work of Tyler and Fagan (2008) who discuss how perceptions of procedural injustice, such as arbitrary detention, lead to decreased willingness to report crimes due to fear that interactions with law enforcement may be dangerous or unjust. This breakdown in trust is critical, as communities must feel that law enforcement operates fairly and ethically to engage with it effectively. According to Transparency International (2020), accountability mechanisms are essential for maintaining community trust. When law enforcement lacks accountability and engages in practices like unlawful detention, it diminishes confidence in the legal system and discourages crime reporting.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between police ethical practices and crime reporting in Cross River State, Nigeria, with a focus on the effects of police brutality, and unlawful detention, on citizens' willingness to report crimes. After thorough statistical analysis of the hypotheses formulated, the following conclusions were drawn:

Police brutality significantly affects crime reporting, as fear of violence or excessive force deters individuals from approaching law enforcement.

Unlawful detention was found to significantly relate to lower crime reporting rates, as arbitrary detentions foster a climate of distrust and fear.

These findings underscore the importance of ethical and transparent policing practices to build community trust, encourage cooperation with law enforcement, and improve crime reporting rates in Cross River State.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study and the conclusion drawn from the findings, the following recommendations were put forward:

Police authority should organize regular training for police officers on human rights, conflict resolution, and de-escalation techniques in order to reduce incidents of brutality. The government with civil organizations should establish independent oversight bodies to

investigate complaints of police brutality which would help restore public confidence and encourage reporting

Police authority should implement training for police officers that focus on ethics and the consequences of extortion, highlighting its detrimental impact on community relations. Also, the police authority should establish a secure reporting mechanism for victims of police extortion that would encourage individuals to come forward without fear of retaliation. The government should educate the public about their rights and the procedures for reporting extortion, this can empower citizens and reduce the incidence of police misconduct.

There should be regular audits of detention practices by independent bodies like the judiciary that would ensure compliance with legal standards and promote accountability.

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